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METHODS FOR MANAGING THE RELIABILITY AND QUALITY OF IoT SENSORS

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Abstract. *The article presents an analysis of methods for managing the reliability and quality of IoT sensors. An analysis of the factors influencing the performance of sensors at different stages of their life cycle was carried out. Methods for predicting reliability parameters are proposed that make it possible to ensure regulated quality indicators already at the design stage of sensor-transforming equipment.*

Keywords: *sensors, methods for predicting reliability parameters, models for calculating reliability indicators of sensors, predicting sensor reliability, Joule-Lenz law, Boltzmann constant.*

МЕТОДЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ НАДЕЖНОСТЬЮ И КАЧЕСТВОМ IoT-ДАТЧИКОВ

Аннотация. *В статье представлен анализ методов управления надежностью и качеством IoT-датчиков. Проведен анализ факторов, влияющих на работоспособность датчиков на разных этапах их жизненного цикла. Предложены методы прогнозирования параметров надежности, позволяющие обеспечить регламентированные показатели качества уже на этапе проектирования сенсорно-преобразовательной аппаратуры.*

Ключевые слова: *датчики, методы прогнозирования параметров надежности, модели расчета показателей надежности датчиков, прогнозирование надежности датчиков, закон Джоуля-Ленца, постоянная Больцмана.*

Introduction. For consumers of sensors, product quality is a significant issue due to the negative consequences of using low-quality products, since sensor failure can lead to the failure of an entire complex of expensive, high-performance equipment. Monitoring the reliability of an organization is a tool that allows you to increase the efficiency of coordination and control of all business processes, increase the degree of rational use of all types of resources and respond much faster to changes in market conditions. An analysis has been made of the factors influencing the performance of sensors at different stages of their life cycle. Methods for predicting reliability parameters are proposed that make it possible to ensure regulated quality indicators already at the design stage of sensor-converting equipment. The use of models for calculating reliability indicators of sensors, based on predictive information about similar, previously created products, will improve the quality and reliability indicators at the design stages of sensors operating under extreme conditions of exposure to a complex of influencing quantities. The introduction of reliability management into quality management systems of production processes will significantly reduce the costs of development and production of sensor-transforming equipment [1].

Research object and methods. Analysis of methods for ensuring the reliability of sensors at different stages of its life cycle. The modern approach to ensuring the reliability of sensors at the required level is based on two aspects - mechanical and metrological reliability. On the one hand, sensors are part of the design of the objects under study, the parameters of which are measured; on the other hand, they are considered as converters of measurement information with standardized metrological characteristics. At the initial stages of development of sensor engineering, due to the absence of requirements for the mechanical reliability of sensors in the technical specifications (TS), its assessment was carried out mainly based on test results. Increasing requirements for the mechanical reliability of sensors, as well as the complexity and large volume of tests to confirm it, have led to the need to use a calculated assessment of mechanical reliability by constructing and analyzing their structural and functional diagrams. However, such an assessment was carried out, as a

rule, at the final stages of sensor development, and if the mechanical reliability indicators did not meet the established requirements, it led to the need to perform significant work and additional material costs due to changes in their design. These circumstances did not contribute to maintaining competitiveness and sustainable demand for sensor-transforming equipment due to its inefficient design and production, since ultimately all these costs led to a significant increase in development time and cost. In the totality of various areas of research related to the development and application of reliability theory, two large areas can currently be distinguished [2].

The first is the development and application of mathematical methods to the problems of finding and analyzing reliability parameters of systems and elements. Here we mainly use methods of mathematical statistics and probability theory, which have been widely developed recently in their application to reliability theory. Probabilistic-statistical methods in reliability theory are considered in some way as “classics of problem solving”, and the reliability theory itself, built on these methods, is considered “classical”. Another direction is characterized by the development of work related to the study of the physics of failures, processes (mechanical, physical-chemical, electrical, etc.) that lead to certain changes in aging, wear, destruction of materials, improvement or deterioration of their properties.

Research results and their discussion. The reliability characteristics of technical products, including sensors, are usually divided into two groups: qualitative and quantitative. A qualitative definition characterizes the properties of a single product. The concept of reliability is defined by many different quantitative characteristics, and therefore cannot be used to its fullest extent. But, despite this, they often try to use quantitative characteristics of reliability, because qualitative characteristics cannot be expressed mathematically. This led to the need to create new basic criteria that could quantify the reliability of specific elements and evaluate the reliability of products in comparison with each other. The most commonly used reliability criteria are: failure rate (the conditional probability density of the occurrence of an object failure, determined under the condition that a failure did not occur before the considered point

in time); probability of failure-free operation (the probability that an object will not fail within a given operating time); gamma-percentage time to failure (time to failure, during which an object failure will not occur with a probability expressed as a percentage).

The reliability characteristic is understood as a specific quantitative value of the reliability criterion for a specific part. These quantitative values help to calculate reliability, calculate the approximate service life of sensors, and calculate the estimated repair time [3]. Reliability for sensors is, first of all, the ability of a product to perform specified functions, maintaining over time the values of established performance indicators within specified limits corresponding to specified modes and conditions of use, maintenance, repair, storage and transportation under extreme operating conditions. This is a quality that extends over time. Therefore, the concept of reliability is close to the concept of quality, and therefore the problems of quality management are directly reflected in the concept of reliability.

Reliability control as a quality improvement tool. Currently, work is underway to create sensors with elements of self-diagnosis, intellectualize the processes of receiving and processing information, expand the functionality of equipment based on the use of new structural materials, critical technologies, micro- and nanotechnologies.

The main indicators of the quality of sensors, confirmed by many years of practice in their use in technology, are high reliability and performance in difficult operating conditions while maintaining established metrological characteristics. Product quality is ensured at the stages of development, production, testing in accordance with established processes of the quality management system.

An effective and affordable means of improving the quality of sensors and thereby achieving reliability goals is the development and application of a reliability management concept at the enterprise. The concept describes the general processes of the reliability management system and is intended for strategic management of quality policy and coordination of activities to ensure the reliability of sensors, increase their efficiency and improve the financial results of the enterprise. The reliability

management system should include a program for achieving goals in the field of product reliability, providing resources to complete these tasks, monitoring, analyzing performance results and coordinating it in terms of meeting the needs and expectations of consumers.

The reliability program identifies critical factors responsible for achieving sensor reliability objectives, and develops a strategic plan that establishes objectives, methods, sequence of actions to achieve reliability goals, and criteria for measuring performance. The objectives of the reliability program must be maintained, the management infrastructure must maintain communication with the consumer, be flexible and adapt to possible changes. The basic factors that form the necessary basis for the manufacture of high-quality products with specified reliability indicators are the material base of the enterprise (fixed assets, materials and components, measuring instruments, technological and testing equipment, methodological support) and qualified personnel (human factor) [4].

A sensor goes through a number of stages in its life cycle. Each stage, from design to dismantling and disposal, is usually accompanied by measurements of a number of product characteristics used to assess whether they are of the required quality. Particular attention should be paid to the main technical factors influencing the quality of the technological process of manufacturing sensors, these include: the state of technical documentation, the degree of equipment and automation of process and testing equipment, as well as measuring instruments, quality control of materials, raw materials and components. Analysis of the results of the reliability program can be performed on the basis of experimental or analytical assessments of sensor reliability indicators.

Predicting sensor reliability. An effective way to achieve high reliability is to predict the reliability indicators of products at the early stages of their life cycle. Modeling changes in critical parameters of products under normal and severe operating conditions and operating modes provides an analytical approach to determining reliability indicators. This approach makes it possible to ensure timely fulfillment of

reliability requirements when implementing long-term projects while maximizing the use of available resources. Prediction methods and algorithms must be correct, based on experimental test data of products, analogues, technical models and samples, and take into account the influence of operating conditions and workloads.

Scientific research results and conclusion. Traditionally, the probability of failure-free operation of designed sensors has been assessed based on the condition of meeting the requirement:

$$P_p \geq P_z, \quad (1)$$

where P_p and P_z are the calculated and specified values of the probability of failure-free operation of the sensor, respectively. In this case, due to the difficulty or significant error in calculating individual elements or nodes of the sensor, the average value of the coefficient of variation found from the results of an experimental study and statistical processing of a certain amount of information was used in its design assessment.

Currently, the widespread use of high-performance computing technology makes it possible to use methods for assessing reliability indicators based on formalized descriptions and models. This made it possible to use empirical dependences of product reliability indicators on the operating mode of the sensors. These dependencies form the basis of the so-called accelerated reliability tests, which are based on models that describe changes in the electrical parameters of sensors over time. Accelerated tests are based on the use of forced modes and the use of prediction theory. Forced tests are based on the intensification of degradation processes leading to failure of the sensor under test.

Two methods can be used to assess sensor reliability indicators. The first method is based on studying the physicochemical processes occurring in the sensor under study. In this case, the current state of the product is described by equations that reflect the physical laws of its aging [5].

The second method is based on the study of statistical, probabilistic patterns of behavior of sensor suitability criteria and requires large amounts of accumulated statistical information based on test results. It is obvious that at the current level of

development of electronic technology, methods for assessing sensor reliability indicators must combine statistical research methods with the study of physical laws, changes in the properties and parameters of products, and descriptions of the kinetics of processes that cause these changes.

The use of models that describe the physical and chemical processes of sensors makes it possible to develop scientifically based methods for accelerated testing and methods for predicting the values of reliability indicators, which will reduce the volume and duration of the necessary expensive reliability tests. When using statistical methods, the assumption is made that in the presence of established technology or established production, the once obtained empirical relationship between quantitative indicators of reliability and quantitative characteristics of external influences is preserved, allowing an accelerated method to monitor the reliability of batches of products. Analysis of the data obtained allows us to conclude that if the calculation uses information from the test results of products, the nature of the failure of which is associated with the natural “aging” of materials, then the results obtained fairly objectively reflect the performance of potentiometers over a long time. If sensor failures are associated with a violation of the technological process, then the values of reliability indicators turn out to be significantly underestimated.

When using methods based on the analysis of physical and chemical processes, the type of relationship between quantitative indicators of reliability and quantitative characteristics of external influences is determined analytically based on consideration of the adopted model of the influence of physical and chemical processes on the reliability of sensors [6].

Probabilistic physical methods for assessing sensor reliability indicators are used when, based on the results of preliminary studies, the degradation process can be approximated by a continuous Markov process of the diffusion type, i.e. the process under study is controlled by a first-order stochastic differential equation:

$$dx(t) = A(t)dt + B(t)d\eta(t), \quad (2)$$

where $x(t)$ is the determining parameter; $A(t)$, $B(t)$ – deterministic functions characterizing the change in the average value and dispersion of the defining parameter (coefficients of the defining parameter); $\eta(t)$ is a random component of Gaussian type.

For example, the change in the electrical resistance of the sensor over time is due to the processes of oxidation, diffusion and reactions in solids. In all cases, the rate of physical and chemical processes occurring in the sensor material is a function of the temperature of the material and has a temperature dependence determined by the Arrhenius law:

$$\tau^{-1} = v_0 \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-E_a}{kT}\right), \quad (3)$$

where v_0 is the frequency multiplier; E_a – activation energy; τ^{-1} – relaxation rate; k – Boltzmann constant.

During operation, various physical and chemical processes occur in the materials used to manufacture sensors, which can lead to significant deviations of sensor parameters from their nominal values. When electric current passes through the sensor, heat is generated. The amount of heat released per unit time is determined by the Joule-Lenz law. Over the volume of the sensor material in a stationary mode, a certain temperature distribution is established, determined by the design of the product and the current flowing through it. Any process leading to a change in structure and composition is determined by the movement of atoms and ions, i.e. diffusion. The rate of diffusion is determined by the diffusion coefficient, which depends on temperature and activation energy [7].

For example, the dependence of the change in complex resistance over time on temperature, load and intensity of its activation is presented as:

$$Z = Z_0 e^{\frac{-B}{T}} P^\beta (1 + af) f(\tau), \quad (4)$$

where Z is the relative change in resistance (suitability criterion); Z_0 – coefficient having the dimension of the suitability criterion parameter; B – energy coefficient,

characterized by the activation energy of the sensor; T – temperature; P – electrical load; f – inclusion intensity; α – cyclicity coefficient; $f(\tau)$ – time parameter.

Modern methods of forced accelerated testing are based on increasing the speed of physical and chemical processes that arise when environmental conditions and operating modes change and affect the properties and characteristics of materials. Changes in failure mode over time and as a function of impact magnitude limit the ability of accelerated testing. The permissible limit for increasing the influencing quantity is limited to its value at which new processes arise that differ from the processes observed under nominal operating conditions. It is recommended to increase the temperature and electrical load to speed up processes leading to failures of electrical elements [8].

When extrapolating the results of accelerated tests to another temperature, the following assumptions are made: a set of several reactions is considered as one, the Arrhenius equation is used to determine the activation energy. The theoretical dependence of the maximum possible acceleration coefficient (k_y) on the activation energy value, obtained on the basis of the Arrhenius law, has the form:

$$k_y = \exp \frac{E_a}{k} \left(\frac{1}{T_n} - \frac{1}{T_f} \right), \quad (5)$$

where T_n is the temperature of the sensor under normal conditions; T_f – sensor temperature at the actual reliability test temperature.

Accelerated reliability tests in forced modes make it possible to evaluate the reliability of sensor-converting equipment at the early stages of its life cycle [9].

Final conclusion. Thus, the main ways to ensure and improve the reliability of sensor-transforming equipment is effective reliability control, based on: 1) managing the supply of materials, raw materials and components with improved properties and technical characteristics and organizing their incoming inspection; 2) development of a methodology for analyzing possible defects in sensors, methods and methods for their identification; 3) carrying out measures to improve the technology of manufacturing

products through a scientifically based selection of control procedures and compliance with all requirements of the technological process of manufacturing products; 4) increasing the efficiency of testing using automated information and measuring testing systems with hardware that has high metrological characteristics and the ability to create real operating conditions; 5) development of algorithms and methods for processing data from test results based on the analysis of physical processes leading to failures and statistical methods for assessing reliability indicators, making it possible to predict the reliability indicators of sensors at the early stages of their life cycle.

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